

PATTERN OF USING SOCIAL MEDIA AND ITS IMPACT ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF SCHOOL GOING ADOLESCENTS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract:

The social media has very much popular and impacted students' psychological wellbeing, daily routines. Students uses social media sites like Snapchat, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp for academic, enjoyment, communication, information exchange, and friendship-building purposes. The researcher focused on the pattern of using social media and its impact on psychological well-being of school going adolescents. The researcher used the descriptive survey method to complete this study. The researcher also used a random sampling technique based on a Likert Five-point scale to collect data from 200 school going adolescents. For measuring the pattern of using social media and its impact on psychological well-being, the researcher used two self-made questionnaires, a questionnaire (10 items) on pattern of using social media and also used another questionnaire (16 items) on impact of social media on psychological wellbeing. For data analysis, the researcher developed a flow chart, graphical representation to represent the pattern of using social media and also used SPSS-23 to compute the Mean, S.D., t-test, ANOVA. Results of the study reported that the use of social media had a positive impact on psychological well-being of the school going adolescents. Additionally, it was discovered that 100% of school-going adolescents use various forms of social media in their daily lives. Besides, the study revealed that there is no significant mean difference in the impact of psychological wellbeing of school going adolescents based on some demographics such as gender, academic grade, age. The findings also revealed that there is no significant mean difference in the impact of psychological wellbeing of school going adolescents based on social media use in a week, social media use in a day. However, the results indicate that 93.5% adolescents use social media for academic purposes, and also enjoyment, communication, information exchange, and friendship-building purposes.

Keywords: Social Media, Impact, Psychological Wellbeing, School Going Adolescents.

Introduction:

Interpersonal communication is essential for satisfying the basic desires of humans to belong and connect (Baumeister & Leary, 1995). The methods of interpersonal communication have seen a significant transformation in recent decades due to the development of information technology, particularly with the fast spread of Internet-based social media (such as Facebook, Twitter, WeChat, or Instagram) (Smith & Anderson, 2018; Stone, & Wang, 2018). It has been shown that social media addiction is linked to a wide range of emotional, relationship, health, and performance issues (Spada et

al., 2008). Adolescents who use social media face a risk to their mental well-being. The internet is now a cutting-edge means of communication for people and families thanks to recent advancements in technology. Over the last ten years, social media sites have produced an online phenomenon that has grown in popularity (Sponcil & Gitimu, 2021).

Additionally, social media has improved and communicated how pupils learn, how they study, and the general situation (Khatib & Khan, 2017). Even while using social media regularly has good impacts on a person, it also has drawbacks. Several Addiction to social media poses serious risks to teens' mental and physical health (Hall & Liu, 2022). Adolescents use social media to connect with others, but this culture of comparison often has a harmful impact on their mental health (Tibber & Silver, 2022). According to several studies, adolescents who are addicted to social media sites like Snapchat, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and WhatsApp experience more negative side effects like eyestrain, social withdrawal, sleep deprivation, feelings of depression and anxiety, loneliness and poor body image, cyberbullying, and low self-esteem (Singh et al., 2020). Many parents and educators are concerned that their university students are not spending enough time studying and are instead spending too much time on Facebook and other social media platforms (Chaudhary & sahani, 2017).

Youngsters have very poor psychological wellness as a result of social media platforms all around the world. As a result, the focus of this study is on pattern of using Social Media and its impact on psychological well-being of school going adolescents (Mana and Barman, 2020).

Need and significance of the study:

The present study enhances our knowledge of how school-going adolescents use social media. The study also highlights on the significant impacts social media use patterns have on the psychological wellbeing of adolescent students. Researchers, scholars, and readers will be able to determine how often the majority of school-going adolescents used to social media each day. Therefore, the impact of social media on adolescents' psychological wellbeing were discussed in this paper.

Review of related literature:

In this study, the researcher examined and summarized the vast majority of relevant research papers on the Pattern of Using Social Media and Its Impact on Psychological Well-Being that had been done in India and abroad.

In order to determine how social media usage influences students' self-concept, Best et al. (2014) conducted a study on how college students using social media. The study's findings showed that every college student who was examined used at least one social networking website. Chaudhary & sahani (2017) looked at a study on the effects of social media on college students. The study's findings show that even though most college students use social media and spend a lot of time on these websites, there are drawbacks to being a student. Poor academic performance was discovered when Khatib and Khan (2017) examined and analysed the impact of social media on students' academic performance and social interpersonal skills. Impact of developing technologies in social media on schooling was examined in a different research by Kaur and Gupta (2018). The findings suggested that using various social media technologies had deeper educational advantages. In an investigation on social media usage and adolescent mental health conducted by Kelly et al. (2018), it was shown that females were more likely than boys to have a significant correlation between social media use and depressive symptoms. Another research by Hou et al. (2019) demonstrates that passive social media usage during the COVID-19 pandemic is inversely correlated with felt stress via both upward and downward social comparison. According to Singh et al. (2020) investigation on the effects of social media on mental health, there is a substantial difference in the levels of sadness, anxiety, and stress in teenagers who use social media for

less than two hours compared to those who use it for more than two hours. Dienlin and Johannes (2020) looked at how using digital technology affected adolescents' wellbeing. The study's findings were that using digital technology has more of an impact on short-term indicators of heuristic well-being than it does on long-term indicators of eudemonic well-being. The gap between population-level trends and those between within-person and inter-person displacement is examined in this article. Another study by Sponcil & Gitimu (2021) examined the relationship between social media and adolescent wellbeing and found that negative impacts like increased risk of injury, social isolation, depression, and cyberbullying were reported. In contrast to the findings reported by Hall et al. (2022) that support social displacement. On the other hand, Wolfers and Utz's study from 2022 on social media usage, stress, and coping shows that it may both relieve stress and act as a resource. The study shows that social media may lead to stress, be a source of resources, and be a tool for different coping mechanisms, but it's still not apparent when social media can effectively reduce stress. Salafia & Diplacido (2022) looked at the relationship between social media use and vaping among college students as well as how social norms, perceptions, and motivations affected this relationship. The findings showed that higher levels of vaping were connected with increased social media usage, a more favourable perception of electronic cigarettes, and social norms. According to Winstone et al. (2022), adolescents who share a large amount of information online, in addition to texting and surfing, are considered broadcasters and are most likely to have poor mental health one year later. According to Ulvi et al. (2022), although excessive and growing use of social media, especially among those who are susceptible, is linked to depression and other mental health conditions, even if it may foster a user's feeling of community.

Keeping in mind all these things, the investigators felt that this is a very important area where more and more research studies are needed to be carried out to explore in-depth results regarding pattern of using social media and its impact on psychological well-being of school going adolescents. As a result, the investigator decided to chosen this study.

Research Question:

- What is the social media use pattern of school going adolescents?
- For what reasons are adolescents using social media?

Objectives of the Study:

The investigator has conducted his study on the basis of the following objectives:

- To study the pattern of using social media among the school-going adolescents.
- To study the impact of social media on psychological well-being of school- going adolescents.
- To find out the impact of social media on psychological well-being of school- going adolescents based on gender, age, academic grade, how long social media use for, how many days use social media in a week, time and duration of using social media in a day.

Hypotheses of the Study:

H0₁: There exist no significant mean differences on impact of Social Media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents.

H0₂: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on Gender.

H0₃: There exist no significant mean differences on impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on Age.

H0₄: There exist no significant mean differences on impact of social media on Psychological Well-being

of school-going adolescents based on Academic Grade.

H05: There exist no significant mean differences on impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on how long social media use for.

H06: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on how many days use social media in a week.

H07: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on Time Duration of using Social Media in a day.

Methods and Participants:

The present study was a survey based descriptive study. The study was conducted on 200 students from the various secondary schools under the Uttar Dinajpur district of West Bengal. The sample of the study has been selected using on random sampling technique (Ghosh and Barman, 2019). The present investigator used SPSS 23 to analyses Mean, S.D, “t”- test, ANOVA.

Research Tools Used:

The accuracy of the result is determined by the tools used for evaluation purpose. In the current study the researcher has created and used two different questionnaires. The questionnaire was distributed via A4 size paper. A total of 200 responses were collected and analyzed accordingly.

- A scale on Pattern of Using Social Media.
- A scale on Impact of social media on psychological wellbeing.

About the tools	Items		Scoring Principles		Reliability	
	Close ended	Total Items	For positive items	For negative items	Reliability Value	Classification
			Direct Scoring	Reverse Scoring		
1. Pattern Of Using Social Media.	10	10	Strongly Agree-5 Agree-4 Neutral-3 Disagree-2 Strongly Disagree-1	Strongly Agree-1 Agree-2 Neutral-3 Disagree-4 Strongly Disagree-5	0.88	Good
2. Impact of social media on psychological wellbeing.	16	16	Strongly Agree-5 Agree-4 Neutral-3 Disagree-2 Strongly Disagree-1	Strongly Agree-1 Agree-2 Neutral-3 Disagree-4 Strongly Disagree-5	0.76	Be Accepted

Table1: Description of the tools

Results and Interpretation:

A) Pattern of Using Social Media of School Going Adolescents:

The Pattern of Using Social Media of School Going Adolescents was determined using a Likerts’ scale. A graphical representation of the findings of this aspect is shown below:

Figure1: The graphical representation of the number and percentage of using different aspect of social media.

Source: Primary data (collected by Researcher, 2022)

From the above figure shows that 52 (or 26%) of 200 school-going adolescent students use Facebook, WhatsApp, and YouTube. Additionally, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and YouTube are used by 24 students (12%), in addition to 26 students (13%) who use them. 15 students (7.5%) use YouTube and WhatsApp. 14 students, or 7%, only use Facebook. Facebook and YouTube are used by 12 (6%) of the students. Also Students in class 9 (4.5%) use Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, and other platforms. Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube are used by 5 (2.5%) of the students. Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and other platforms are used by 5 (2.5%) of the students. 5 (2.5%) students use YouTube, Instagram, and WhatsApp. Four (2%) of the students use Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, and other platforms. Four students exclusively use WhatsApp. A total of 4 (2%), including 3 others, use Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, and YouTube. 3 people use WhatsApp.

Figure 3: Observed pattern of using social media based on yearly usage, weekly usage, number of hours spent.

Source: Primary data (collected by Researcher, 2022)

The above figure shows that Out of 200 Students, 46%, 24%, 14% and 16% Students use Social Media 1 year, 1-2 years 2-3 years and more than 3 years. As a result, it can be stated that the highest percentage of School going adolescents are using social media. On the other hand, out of 200 Students, 100% Students are using different aspects of Social Media. As a result, it can be stated that 100% of school-going adolescents use various forms of social media in their daily lives. 70% student use social media every day in a week (Ghosh and Barman, 2019). It also discovered that out of 200 students, 35.5%, 34.5%, 11.5%, and 18.5% use social media for one hour, two hours, three hours, or more per day. Thus, it can be concluded that school-going adolescents use social media for longer than an hour and for a couple of hours.

B) Impact of social media on Psychological Wellbeing of School Going Adolescents:

Name of the tool (questionnaire)	Criteria/Scores for Considering the Level of Impact		
Impact of social media on psychological wellbeing.	Respective Neutral Points	Good/Positive	Bad/Negative
	48	> 48	< 48

Table2: Level of Impact of Social Media on Psychological Well-Being of School going Adolescents.

From the above table 2 it was observed that out of the total 200 Students 52% students have scored above and less than 48 % students have scored below on the impact of Social Media on Psychological Well-Being scale towards School going Adolescents. Therefore, we can conclude that the majority of students (52 percent) scored between 48 and > 48, indicating moderate to high impact of Social Media on Psychological Well-Being among School going Adolescents.

Demographic Variables		Number (N)	Mean (M)	SD (σ)	Test Employed
Gender	Male	104	55.26	6.838	t-test
	Female	96	56.29	7.059	
Age Group	Upto16	144	55.61	6.595	t-test
	Above 16	56	56.13	7.830	
Academic Grade	IX	48	55.33	6.774	ANOVA
	X	52	56.25	6.271	
	XI	48	54.35	6.145	
	XII	52	56.94	8.257	

Table 3: Summary of the Mean and SD in pattern of social media & its impact on psychological wellbeing in school going adolescents.

H0₁: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of Social Media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents.

Name of the tool	Number of Items	Neutral Points	Means	S.D	df	t-value	Result
Impact of social media on psychological wellbeing.	16	48	55.75	6.93	199	15.85	Significant at 0.05 level*

Table 4: The significant mean difference using Social Media on Psychological Well-being of school-going Adolescents.

From table 4 it can be observed that the calculated 't'-value is 15.85 and it is greater than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 199 degree of freedom (df). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and it imply the result is significant and it indicates that the use of social media has a positive impact on psychological well-being of the school going adolescents.

H0₂: There exist no significant mean difference on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on Gender.

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	SED	df	t-value	Result
Male	104	55.26	6.838	1.03	0.983	199	1.050	<i>Not Significant at 0.05 level*</i>
Female	96	56.29	7.059					

Table 5: The significant mean difference between Male and Female Students regarding impact of social media on Psychological Well-being.

From table 5 it can be observed that the calculated 't'-value is 1.050 and it is less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 199 degree of freedom (df). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and it imply the result is insignificant and we may conclude that there is no significant difference among the male and female Students regarding impact of social media on Psychological well-being.

H0₃: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on Age.

Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference	SED	df	t-value	Result
Upto 16	144	55.61	6.59	.514	1.096	198	.469	<i>Not Significant at 0.05 level*</i>
Average 16	56	56.13	7.83					

Table 6: The significant mean difference between up to 16 and average 16 Students regarding impact of social media on Psychological Well-being.

From table 6 it can be observed that the calculated 't'-value is 0.469 and it is less than the critical value at 0.05 level of significance with 198 degree of freedom (df). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted and it imply the result is insignificant and we may conclude that there is no significant mean difference between up to 16 and average 16 Students regarding impact of social media on their Psychological Well-being.

H0₄: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on Academic Grade.

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	188.77	3	62.924	1.310	.272
Within Groups	9414.22	196	48.032		
Total	9602.99	199			

Table 7: Showing the differences among the school going adolescents regarding the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being based on Academic grade.

*At 0.05 level of Significance 2.65

*At 0.01 level of significance 3.88

From the above table it can be observed that the calculated F-value is less than the critical value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is failed to reject at both level of significance. Hence, it can be interpreted that there is no significant mean difference among the school going adolescents regarding the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being based on Academic grade.

H0₅: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on how long social media use for.

Groups/Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
One Year	92	55.26	6.681
1-2 Years	48	55.29	7.543
2-3 Years	28	58.00	6.336
More than 3 Years	32	55.91	7.204
Total	200	55.76	6.947

Table 8: Number, Mean and S.D of the impacts of social media on psychological well- being of school going adolescent based on how long social media use for.

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	174.620	3	58.207	1.210	.307
Within Groups	9428.37	196	48.104		
Total	9602.99	199			

Table 9: Showing the differences among psychological well- being of school going adolescent based on how long social media use for.

*At 0.05 level of Significance 2.65

*At 0.01 level of significance 3.88

From the above table it can be observed that the calculated F-value is less than the critical value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is failed to reject at both level of significance. Hence, it can be interpreted that there is no significant mean difference among psychological well- being of school going adolescents based on how long social media use for.

H0₆: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on how many days use social media in a week.

Groups/Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1-3 days	39	55.49	6.557
3-6 days	21	57.38	7.940
Everyday	140	55.59	6.915
Total	200	55.76	6.947

Table 10: Number, Mean and S.D social media on psychological well-being of school going

adolescent based on how many days use social media in a week.

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	62.328	2	31.164	.643	.527
Within Groups	9540.66	197	48.430		
Total	9602.99	199			

Table11: Showing the differences social media on psychological well-being of school going adolescent based on how many days use social media in a week.

*At 0.05 level of Significance 3.04

*At 0.01 level of significance 4.71

From the above table it can be observed that the calculated F-value is less than the critical value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is failed to reject at both level of significance. Hence, it can be interpreted that there is no significant mean difference impact of social media on psychological well-being of school going adolescent based on how many days use social media in a week.

H0: There exist no significant mean differences on the impact of social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on Time Duration of using Social Media in a day.

Groups/Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1 Hour	71	55.54	7.079
1-2 Hours	69	56.30	7.111
2-3 Hours	23	54.48	5.575
More than 3 Hours	37	55.95	7.284
Total	200	55.76	6.947

Table12: Number, Mean and S.D of different between impacts of social media on psychological well-being of school going adolescent based on time & duration of using Social Media in a day.

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	63.-093	3	21.031	.432	.730
Within Groups	9539.90	196	48.673		
Total	9602.99	199			

Table13: Showing the differences between impacts of social media on psychological well-being of school going adolescent based on time & duration of using Social Media in a day.

*At 0.05 level of Significance 2.65

*At 0.01 level of significance 3.88

From the above table it can be observed that the calculated F-value is less than the critical value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is failed to reject at both level of significance. Hence, it can be interpreted that there is no significant mean difference between impacts of social media on psychological well-being of school going adolescent based on time & duration of using Social Media in a day.

Discussion:

- The study revealed that out of 200 Students, 100% Students are using different aspects of Social Media. As a result, it can be stated that 100% of school-going adolescents use various forms of social media in their daily lives. 70% student use social media every day in a week (Ghosh and Barman, 2019). On the other hand, out of 200 Students, 46%, 24%, 14% and 16% Students use Social Media 1 year, 1-2 years 2-3 years and more than 3 years. As a result, it can be stated that the highest percentage of School going adolescents are using social media.
- It was found that out of 200 students, 35.5%, 34.5%, 11.5%, and 18.5% use social media for one hour, two hours, three hours, or more per day. Thus, it can be concluded that school-going adolescents use social media for longer than an hour and for a couple of hours. Besides, social media is used by 42.5%, 37.5%, and 7.5% of them in the afternoon, evening, and morning, respectively. Therefore, it can be said that school going adolescent are using social media more than afternoon and night.
- It was discovered that 93.5% of them used social media for academic purposes, while only 6.5% did not. Thus, it can be stated that the highest percentage (93.5%) of the school going adolescents are using social media for academic purpose. On the other hand, 100% adolescents use social media for academic, enjoyment, communication, information exchange, and friendship-building purposes. It is found that 100% students are watching educational matter on various social media apps like that Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter and YouTube and using social media for academic, entertainment, communication, information exchange and making friends purpose. And 27% students mostly using social media for academic purpose.
- Results revealed that the use of social media had a positive impact on psychological well-being of the school going adolescents.
- The study also revealed that there is no significant difference among the impact of using social media on Psychological Well-being of school-going adolescents based on gender, age, academic grade, how long social media use for, how many days use social media in a week and time duration of using Social Media in a day.

Limitations of the Study:

The limitation of the current study are as follows:

- Only the secondary level students in West Bengal's Uttar Dinajpur District are included in the present investigation.
- Only 200 students from the secondary level institutions in the Uttar Dinajpur District were selected as the sample for the current study by the researcher.
- The current research was conducted on a few particular student demographic characteristics, such as education levels, gender, Age (Das and Sarkar, 2022).

Conclusion:

The present study shows that most of the school going adolescents is using social media platforms like Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube etc. for the purpose of academic, entertainment, communication, making friend and information exchange and some of them are using social media 1-2 days a week and some 2-3 days and many of students are using social media more than three days. The objectives of this study were find out the pattern of social media is used by school-going adolescents and its impact on their psychological well-being. The result of the study revealed that social media has positive impact on their psychological well-being. Investigations have demonstrated that adolescents who are in school are very active on social media, spending the bulk of their waking hours on these sites. However, social media has deeply embedded itself strongly into adolescents' daily lives, and they use it frequently and for extended periods of time for a variety of purposes.

Recommendations for Further Study:

- A similar study can be conducted by including larger samples from various areas as well as from different levels (Das and Singha, 2022).
- A comparative study can be conducted on Pattern of Using Social Media and it's on Psychological Well-Being of School Going Adolescent among College and School level students in West Bengal as well as in India.
- A further study can be carried out on subjective well-being in respect of impact of social media in the elementary and secondary level students from different part of the country.

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